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Assessing the interaction between the N-terminal region of the membrane protein magnesium transporter A and a lipid bilayer

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the interaction of KEIF, the intrinsically disordered N-terminal region of the magnesium transporter MgtA, with lipid bilayers mimicking cell membranes. Combining experimental techniques such as neutron reflectometry (NR), quartz-crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D), synchrotron radiation circular dichroism (SRCD), and oriented circular dichroism (OCD), with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, we characterized KEIF's adsorption behavior.

Hypothesis: KEIF undergoes conformational changes upon interacting with lipid bilayers, potentially influencing MgtA's function within the plasma membrane.

Experiments: The study assessed KEIF's structural transitions and position within lipid bilayers under various conditions, including zwitterionic versus anionic bilayers and different salt concentrations. The techniques analyzed adsorption-induced structural shifts and peptide localization within the bilayer.

Findings: KEIF transitions from a disordered to a more structured state, notably increasing α -helical content upon adsorption to lipid bilayers. The peptide resides primarily in the hydrophobic tail region of the bilayer, where it may displace lipids. Electrostatic interactions, modulated by bilayer charge and ionic strength, play a critical role.

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These results suggest that KEIF's conformational changes and bilayer interactions can be integral to its potential modulatory role in MgtA function within the plasma membrane.

This research highlights the importance of surface-induced structural transitions in intrinsically disordered proteins and their implications for membrane protein modulation.

1. Introduction

The magnesium ion (Mg^{2+}) is an essential mineral nutrient for all cells in living organisms and is the most abundant divalent cation in any biological system [1]. It is, therefore, vital for organisms to transport it. In bacteria, three classes of Mg^{2+} transporters have been identified as responsible for the translocation of Mg^{2+} across the cell membrane [2]. One of them, MgtA [3], consists of 898 amino acids and has a molecular weight of 99.466 kDa (Uniprot entry: P0ABB8). In a study by Subramani et al., 2016 [4], using the DISOPRED3 server for intrinsically disordered region (IDR) prediction [5], the first 33 amino acids (1-33) of MgtA from *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) were classified as intrinsically disordered. Intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) lack a unique, singular equilibrium structure and instead sample a heterogeneous ensemble of conformations in solution [6–8]. It has been shown that ~30% of all proteins in eukaryotic organisms belong to this group of proteins. Despite their lack of equilibrium structure, IDPs are involved in many central biological processes. This fact challenges the traditional protein structure paradigm, which states that a specific, well-defined structure is required for protein function.

In the present paper, the N-terminal IDR of MgtA is referred to as KEIF and has the following amino acid primary structure:

M F **K** **E** **I** **F** T R L I R H L P S R L V H R **D** P L P G A
Q Q T V N T V.

KEIF carries five positively charged (blue) amino acids at physiological pH and two negatively charged (red) amino acids (For interpretation of the colors, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.), giving it a net charge of +3. Most charged amino acids are evenly distributed in the first half of the peptide. In our previous study on physicochemical characterization of KEIF [9], we showed, using circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy and small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments, as well as molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, that KEIF indeed displays the typical characteristics of an IDP in aqueous bulk solution, thus corroborating Subramani's DISOPRED3-based prediction [4]. In contrast to primary structure analysis that predicted a somewhat globular conformation of KEIF, both SAXS and MD simulation results suggested that KEIF is fully flexible and relatively extended. Considering the relatively high density of cationic amino acid residues in the first half of the peptide, extension can be expected due to local electrostatic repulsion.

In the same study [9], insight into the biochemical function of KEIF was provided as it was shown using CD spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, laser Doppler velocimetry, and cryogenic transmission electron microscopy that KEIF adsorbs to the surface of anionic lipid bilayers provided by large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs). Because of their opposite charges, the peptide-lipid bilayer interaction was presumed to be electrostatic and entropically driven by the release of counterions. Interestingly, CD spectroscopy revealed adsorption to the vesicle surface concurrent with a conformational change in KEIF, inducing increased α -helical content. This observation supports the common hypothesis that surface-active IDPs, on adsorption to surfaces, adopt a structure that activates their function. It is, therefore, of interest to relate the solution properties (structure/conformation) of IDPs to their properties in the adsorbed state, which will help us to decipher the structure-function relationships in play and, thereby, better understand how IDPs perform their functions.

KEIF is used as a model peptide to investigate the structure-function relationship further. The present paper features a comprehensive characterization of the KEIF's adsorption to model membranes in the form of phospholipid bilayers, which has been performed using an approach combining experimental techniques such as neutron reflectometry (NR), quartz-crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D), synchrotron radiation CD (SRCD), and oriented CD spectroscopy (OCD), with MD simulations. The composition of the phospholipid bilayers was altered from zwitterionic to anionic to investigate the importance of the electrostatic interactions in the system. By performing this study, with KEIF being a typical 'model' IDP, the current study helps deepen our understanding of the general underlying physics that, on the molecular level, governs the surface adsorption-induced conformational changes associated with IDP function.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Peptide solutions

Synthetic KEIF (3.871 kDa) with a 95.67% purity was purchased from Genemed Synthesis Inc. (USA). To remove impurities, the peptide was dissolved in and dialyzed (100–500 Da MWCO Biotech Cellulose Ester (CE) Dialysis Membrane Tubing, SpectrumLabs, Greece) against Milli-Q water at 6 °C. The sample was then lyophilized to obtain the purified peptide. The concentration for the SRCD spectroscopy samples was determined from the absorbance at 205 nm [10]. The concentration was set by the weight-to-volume ratio of the peptide powder and buffer solution for the other techniques.

2.2. Vesicle preparation and vesicle fusion protocol

1-Palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) and 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phospho-L-serine (POPS) were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (USA). Stock solutions were prepared in a 3:7 (v/v) methanol:chloroform mixture using the following lipid molar ratios (%POPC:%POPS): 1:0, 9:1, 3:1. These samples are indicated as PC₉:PS₁, except the 1:0 ratio, which is denoted PC.

Lipid films were formed by evaporating the methanol (100%, VWR, France):chloroform ($\geq 99.8\%$, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) solvent mixture under nitrogen flow, where any remaining solvent was dried under reduced pressure (0.8 bar). The films were hydrated in buffer solution with designated NaCl. For QCM-D and NR measurements, the film was hydrated in 20 mM tris(hydroxymethyl)-aminomethane (TRIS $\geq 99.9\%$, Savearn Werner, Sweden) buffer at pH 7.4 with either 10 mM sodium chloride (NaCl $\geq 99.5\%$, Merck, Germany) for the pure PC sample or 500 mM NaCl for the PC₉:PS₁ sample. The lipid films used in SRCD- and OCD spectroscopy were hydrated in a buffer solution containing 10 mM sodium fluoride (NaF 99.5%, VWR, Germany), 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer (NaH₂PO₄ $\geq 99.0\%$, Sigma Aldrich, Germany and Na₂HPO₄ 98.5 – 101.0%, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) at pH 7.4. LUVs were obtained by extrusion 31 times through a 0.1 μ m polycarbonate membrane filter (Avanti Polar Lipids, USA).

Protocol for vesicle fusion [11,12] was optimized by QCM-D measurements on silicon dioxide-coated sensors. In brief, the injection of LUVs was done in either 500 mM NaCl, or 10 mM NaCl, depending on the lipid composition (500 mM for PC₉:PS₁ and 10 mM for PC). The LUVs were incubated for 60 min followed by a rinsing step with 10 mM

NaCl buffer (20 mM TRIS at pH 7.4) to induce osmotic shock (for the PC₉:PS₁ sample). This resulted in reproducible, high-quality bilayers. More detailed information can be found in Gerelli et al. [13].

2.3. Synchrotron radiation and oriented circular dichroism spectroscopy

SRCD spectroscopy was used to characterize the secondary structure elements present in KEIF in solution and the vicinity of LUVs (PC₉:PS₁ and PC₃:PS₁). The peptide was mixed with a 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4 mass ratio with the LUVs. Samples were dissolved in 10 mM NaF, 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer (H₂NaO₄P and HNa₂O₄P) at pH 7.4. OCD spectroscopy measurements were performed to obtain information about structural elements present in KEIF in a film, as well as the orientation of the peptide to a PC₃:PS₁ membrane.

2.3.1. In solution

Measurements were performed at the AU-CD beam line on the synchrotron light source, ASTRID2, at the Department of Physics and Astronomy, Aarhus University, Denmark. Solution samples were measured in a 0.1 mm quartz cuvette at 20 °C. Five spectra were recorded for each sample between 170 and 280 nm, but for analysis, 177 or 178 nm was used as the lower limit due to high absorbance, depending on the sample. The peptide concentration was roughly 1 mg mL⁻¹ and was determined from the absorbance at 205 nm, which is simultaneously measured on the sample during the CD spectroscopy measurement [10]. A correction by subtracting a reference spectrum (containing only buffer or LUVs in buffer) was performed for all spectra and smoothing using a 7-point window Savitzky-Golay filter. The data was reported as the molar extinction ($\Delta\epsilon$) (cm⁻¹ M⁻¹) according to

$$\Delta\epsilon = \frac{\theta \times (\text{MRW} \times 0.1)}{\frac{c \times L}{3298}}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the measured ellipticity (mdeg), MRW is the mean residue molecular weight, c is the peptide concentration (mg mL⁻¹), and L is the optical path length of the cell (cm). The obtained CD spectra were analyzed and fitted using three different methods: the on-line CD spectroscopy structure analysis tool DichroWeb [14] with the CDSSTR algorithm using the SP175 data set, BeStSel [15,16] (<http://bestsel.elte.hu/index.php>), as well as SELCON3 with the SP175 data set.¹ These different methods gave information on the secondary structure elements present.

2.3.2. The films

For the OCD spectroscopy measurements, thin, uniform films of the samples was produced. This was done following a similar scheme to the one published in Bürck et al. [17], with some variations depending on the sample. All samples containing KEIF and lipids were prepared by mixing LUV with KEIF solution at the desired ratio. 30 μ L of the mixed solution was then pipetted onto a clean quartz window (202-40QS, Hellma Analytics, Germany). The films were left under a protective cover to dry and were then rehydrated in a container with a relative humidity \sim 98 % achieved with a saturated potassium sulfate (K₂SO₄ \geq 99.0%, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) solution. Measurements were performed in the presence of K₂SO₄ solution to ensure the films were hydrated. Windows with the films were placed in a copper holder, with a second clean window enclosing the hydrating solution. This copper holder was placed into a purpose-built computer-controlled rotation stage, fitting into a temperature-controlled chamber. To avoid any linear dichroic effects due to the alignment of the films, the measurement

of the CD spectrum was carried out at four angles, rotating perpendicular to the beam path, such that data was acquired at every 90°, with the 0° measurement repeated to check film stability during measurement. The data was averaged over all angles and presented in terms of mdeg.

2.4. Quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring

QCM-D experiments were performed using a QSense E4 apparatus (Biolin Scientific, Sweden) with four temperature-controlled flow modules. All experiments were conducted on SiO₂-coated AT-cut 5 MHz quartz sensors (Biolin Scientific, Sweden). The sensors were cleaned before use in (consecutively) chloroform, acetone (\geq 99.9%, Sigma Aldrich, USA) and ethanol (96 – 99.5%, Solvaco, Sweden) for 15 min in each solvent, enhanced by sonication. To remove any remaining organic contaminants and to render the surfaces hydrophilic, the surface was treated with air plasma for 3 min (model PDC-3XG, Harrick Plasma, USA), rinsed with Milli-Q water and dried with nitrogen before loaded into the flow module.

Measurements of peptide adsorption were conducted on bare surfaces and for a SLB deposited on top of the surface.

2.4.1. Bare silica surfaces

Experiments were performed with both hydrophilic SiO₂ and hydrophobic (silanized) sensors, where the NaCl concentrations in the former was (10 and 150 mM), and in the latter 10 mM NaCl, respectively. Silanization was performed according to the protocol by Chang et al. [18]. In brief, a clean (hydrophilic) sensor was exposed to air plasma for 3 min, rinsed thoroughly with Milli-Q water, dried under a stream of nitrogen gas, and then immediately placed in a desiccator together with 1 mL of chloro(dimethyl)octylsilane (97%, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The desiccator was evacuated using a vacuum pump for 20 min. After 2 h in the closed desiccator, the sensor was sonicated for 15 min in (consecutively) tetrahydrofuran (THF \geq 99.9%, Sigma Aldrich) and ethanol, to remove any unreacted material. The sensor was then thoroughly rinsed with Milli-Q water and dried under a stream of nitrogen just before being mounted in the flow module.

During the experiments, a baseline was acquired in (20 mM TRIS buffer pH 7.4 supplemented with NaCl). After this stabilization, a 1 mg mL⁻¹ KEIF solution was injected and incubated for 60 min. The system was then rinsed with pristine buffer for another 60 min.

2.4.2. Supported lipid bilayer

Measurements were conducted with a PC bilayer as well as a PC₉:PS₁, for 10 and 150 mM NaCl. After a stable baseline was obtained, SLBs were formed *in situ* on hydrophilic SiO₂ sensors using the vesicle fusion protocol reported by us in ref. [13]. After SLB formation, the same procedure was followed for the KEIF solution, as described above, for the bare surface.

During the QCM-D experiments, data were collected continuously, and to confirm reproducibility. The measurements were performed in at least two replicates, where all datasets were averaged and used for analysis.

2.5. Neutron reflectometry

NR measurements were performed on the time-of-flight reflectometer D17 [19] at Institut Laue-Langevin in Grenoble, France, in the standard geometry for solid-liquid (S/L) measurements using silicon single crystals as solid substrates. A detailed description of the sample environment, cleaning protocols, and experimental procedures used are given in ref. [13]. The instrument was configured to cover a Q range of approximately 0.008 - 0.3 Å⁻¹, where Q is the exchanged wave vector along the vertical direction to the solid-liquid interface. For each sample, reflectivity, R , was measured as a function of Q , wetting the same sample with buffers at different content of H₂O and D₂O, to exploit the contrast variation method [13,20]. These buffers consisted of 20 mM TRIS

¹ The code for SELCON3 was initially made in Matlab in 2005 by the research group of Prof. B.A.Wallace, Birkbeck College, London. The Matlab code was updated in 2006-2007 to allow plotting and calculation of the mean refitted spectrum to the query protein by S.V. Hoffmann, Aarhus University, Denmark. This code was adapted to Python by S.V. Hoffmann, Aarhus University, Denmark, in 2021.

Table 1
Labels to denote the different systems studied, including the salt concentration.

System	Content	Salt concentration [mM]
K ¹⁰	KEIF	10
K ¹⁵⁰	KEIF	150
K-PC ¹⁰	KEIF + POPC	10
K-PC ¹⁵⁰	KEIF + POPC	150
K-PC ₉ PS ₁ ¹⁰	KEIF + PC ₉ PS ₁	10
K-PC ₉ PS ₁ ¹⁵⁰	KEIF + PC ₉ PS ₁	150
K-PC ₃ PS ₁ ¹⁰	KEIF + PC ₃ PS ₁	10

in H₂O supplemented with 10 mM NaCl, hereafter referred to as Hbuf₁₀, and of 20 mM TRIS in D₂O supplemented with 10 mM NaCl, referred to as Dbuf₁₀. Reflectivity was measured in both buffers for the bare substrate before the *in situ* deposition of either a PC or a PC₉:PS₁ SLB. The SLB was then formed by using the vesicle fusion method [11,12] following the same procedure as the one reported by us in ref. [13]. After SLB formation, the sample was rinsed to remove any unbound lipid material, and then the solution was replaced by Dbuf₁₀ and Hbuf₁₀ to acquire NR data. After the characterization of the SLB structure, the buffer was replaced by a solution of KEIF (1 mg mL⁻¹) in Hbuf₁₀. After 60 min of incubation, and before rinsing any unbound material, $R(Q)$ data were acquired in Hbuf₁₀ only. The sample was then rinsed, and $R(Q)$ curves collected in both Hbuf₁₀, Dbuf₁₀ and in a 62:38 Hbuf₁₀:Dbuf₁₀ mixture known as silicon match buffer (SiMbuf), i.e., a solution nullifying the reflectivity from the silicon crystal. All measurements were performed at 20 °C. Raw 2-D detector images were converted into 1-D reflectivity curves, $R(Q)$, using the COSMOS routine provided by the ILL. The global analysis of NR curves was performed using the software Aurore [21]. Data were analyzed using a model consisting of a series of layers, each of them described in terms of scattering length density (SLD) of the dry material, layer thickness (t), buffer volume fraction (f_w), and interfacial roughness (σ). The model for bare substrates consisted of an infinite layer with the SLD of silicon, an oxide layer, and an infinite bulk aqueous layer. As usually done to characterize SLBs, an additional five layers were used to represent the solvent between the oxide and the SLB, and the headgroup and tail regions of the SLB [21]. Upon the addition of KEIF, adding any additional layer to the model was unnecessary since the data could be analyzed by varying the structural parameters of the SLB model.

2.6. Atomistic molecular dynamics simulations

Fully atomistic explicit water MD simulations of systems containing KEIF and lipid bilayers (PC and PC₉:PS₁) were performed using the GROMACS package [22]. An initial linear configuration of KEIF was constructed using Avogadro (Avogadro: an open-source molecular builder and visualization tool. Version 1.2.0) [23]). The zwitterionic state of the N- and C-termini was used, and the basic and acidic amino acids were modeled at physiological pH, giving the peptide a net charge of +3. The systems were built using the CHARMM-GUI Input Generator module for membrane builder, [24–31] where a bilayer composed of either 612 POPC and 68 POPS molecules or only 660 POPC molecules was added to the system. Furthermore, sodium (Na) and chloride (Cl) ions were added to give a NaCl concentration of either 10 or 150 mM, in addition to neutralizing the charges present from the peptide and the bilayer. The CHARMM36m [32] force field together with the TIP3P water model [33,34] was used. Following equilibration, production runs were performed for 1 μ s with a time step of 2 fs in the NPT ensemble, which means that the number of particles, N, the pressure, P, and the temperature, T, were constant. The temperature was kept at 293 K with the Nose–Hoover thermostat, [35,36] and the pressure was controlled with the Parrinello–Rahman barostat [37], and kept at 1 bar. Each system was simulated in three replicas.

All analyses were performed using the GROMACS package [38], and for all systems, the concatenated trajectory of the three replicates,

obtained with `gmx trjconv`, were used. The secondary structure content was determined with `gmx dssp`, which uses the DSSP algorithm. The distance between KEIF and the bilayer was determined with `gmx pairdist` in which the minimum distance between each amino acid and a phosphorus atom was determined. The density of the peptide and the lipid bilayer was obtained with `gmx density`.

3. Results and discussion

In this study, KEIF in several different systems, shown in Table 1 were studied with a variety of techniques, both experimental and computational, which are all presented and discussed to better understand if the peptide gains structure, and therefore also function, upon adsorption to surfaces.

3.1. The effect of KEIF on the lipid bilayer

Information about the interaction of KEIF with a lipid membrane and its location to the latter was investigated using NR and QCM-D for both a purely zwitterionic POPC bilayer and a charged PC₉:PS₁ bilayer at a low NaCl concentration (10 mM), referred to as K-PC¹⁰ and K-PC₉:PS₁¹⁰, respectively. According to the NR measurements, the peptide was found to reside in the tail region of the bilayer, 9.2 % KEIF with 16.5 % solvent for the K-PC¹⁰ system, and 13 % KEIF with 27 % solvent for K-PC₉:PS₁¹⁰. The measured reflectivity curves and their corresponding SLD curves are presented in Fig. 1. In both systems, no KEIF was detected in the hydrophilic headgroup region, whereas a high level of solvent was found, approximately 70 %. The high hydration of the headgroup regions likely stems from KEIF passing through and disturbing the integrity of the bilayer. Independent of the headgroup charge, the peptide is spontaneously incorporated into the hydrophobic region of the bilayer with a similar amount of peptide, indicating that the charge of the headgroup region does not primarily affect the amount of incorporated peptide in the bilayer.

In addition to NR measurements, QCM-D measurements were performed at two NaCl concentrations, 10 and 150 mM, respectively, to assess the electrostatic contribution to the interaction, as well as to obtain information about the time-dependent rearrangements in the system. See Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 for K-PC^{10/150} and K-PC₉:PS₁^{10/150}, respectively. For all systems, there is a splitting between the normalized overtones upon injection and incubation of the peptide, which decreases for all samples upon rinsing with pristine buffer. The splitting and frequency shift is most significant upon injection of KEIF in the K-PC¹⁰ system. The third overtone is, in all systems, starting to display a stepwise curve upon rinsing, and the shape is matched in both frequency and dissipation, which is most likely an artifact originating from electronics and is therefore not considered in the analysis. In all systems, except K-PC₉:PS₁ in 10 mM, the dissipation values return to zero upon rinsing, indicating that the bilayer returns to the same rigidity as before injection of KEIF.

For zwitterionic SLBs, a slight difference in the behavior of the samples measured at 10 mM and 150 mM NaCl was observed. While both frequency shifts and dissipation curves returned to their initial values upon rinsing for the K-PC¹⁰, the data for the K-PC¹⁵⁰ suggest an increase in rigidity, as indicated by the negative dissipation values accompanied by positive frequency shifts. Since the initial value was set to zero for

Fig. 1. Neutron reflectivity data (symbols) and fits (lines) for systems measured after addition of KEIF in 20 mM TRIS, pH 7.4 to a supported lipid bilayer (SLB) composed of POPC at 10 mM NaCl (a), and to a SLB composed of PC₉:PS₁ (c) are shown. Data for the pristine SLBs are not shown. In (b) and (d), SLD profiles corresponding to the models shown in (a) and (c), respectively (solid lines), are shown in comparison with the SLD profiles obtained in the fitting process of the pristine bilayers (dashed lines). For both samples, the splitting of the SLD profiles in the region corresponding to the hydrocarbon core of the SLB ($z \sim 30 - 40 \text{\AA}$) indicates the inclusion of KEIF and water molecules.

the pristine SLBs, positive frequency shifts imply that rinsing removed both protein and lipid molecules from the substrate surface. However, it is not possible to determine the relative amounts of the two molecular species being removed.

Similarly, in all systems except K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰, the normalized frequency shifts converge to positive values after rinsing, while it remains slightly negative for the K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰. These behaviors suggest that more lipid molecules are removed from the samples where $\Delta F_n/n$ reaches positive values. The positive dissipation factor observed for K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰ might indicate a different arrangement of the KEIF molecules to the SLB, with some chains protruding into the solution above the SLB. It is worth recalling that while QCM-D can probe the dynamical effect of a few protruding chains, NR might not capture their presence due to the limited corresponding volume fraction.

A clear difference between the zwitterionic and partially charged bilayers can be observed during the incubation when the pump's flow is stopped. For K-PC¹⁰ and K-PC¹⁵⁰, both the frequency and dissipation shifts remain stable, independent of salt concentration, whereas for K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰ and K-PC₉PS₁¹⁵⁰, the dissipation shifts are slowly decreasing. This behavior indicates time-dependent rearrangements where the system becomes more rigid without adding or removing material, which likely stems from the peptide moving from the top of the bilayer toward the tail region of the bilayer, making the adsorbed layer more rigid. The lack of the corresponding transition in the K-PC systems indicates that

KEIF interacts with the negatively charged headgroups longer before incorporating them in the bilayer, suggesting an electrostatic interaction between the peptide and the headgroups.

Focusing on the electrostatic contribution to the interaction in terms of screening effects, the difference in frequency shift after rinsing with buffer is minimal between the K-PC^{10/150} and K-PC₉PS₁^{10/150}. For the values obtained during incubation, the most significant frequency shift is observed for K-PC¹⁰, while only a minor change is observed for K-PC¹⁵⁰. The initial interaction between KEIF and the PC bilayer seems to have an electrostatic origin; however, it is not very strong due to the headgroup being zwitterionic with a net charge of zero, which is screened by the higher NaCl concentration. This does not seem to affect the final amount of KEIF incorporated into the bilayer, suggesting that a limited amount of the peptides can integrate into the tail region, independent of initial adsorption. During the incubation of KEIF to the K-PC₉PS₁ bilayer, there is only a minor difference in a frequency shift of about -1 Hz between the low and high NaCl concentration.

QCM-D measurements of KEIF adsorbing to a bare silica surface, presented in Figure S1, further support the findings. Here, it was found that upon initial injection, the most significant frequency shift was observed for K¹⁰ on a hydrophilic silica surface followed by K¹⁵⁰ to the same surface, while K¹⁰ injection to a silanized, and therefore hydrophobic silica surface gave rise to a smaller frequency shift. Upon rinsing, the amplitude of the frequency shift is decreased in all three systems. The

Fig. 2. Quartz-crystal microbalance with dissipation data measured for KEIF upon interaction with a PC supported lipid bilayer (SLB) at two different NaCl concentrations, 10 or 150 mM, where data for K-PC¹⁰ is shown in (a) frequency shift, and (b) dissipation shifts of all overtones. K-PC¹⁵⁰ is shown in (c) frequency shifts and (d) dissipation shifts for all overtones.

desorption from the silanized silica was the smallest, leaving this measurement with the largest frequency shift. This result indicates a stronger interaction with the hydrophobic surface than the hydrophilic, even though the adsorption to the latter is more extensive initially. Hence, the electrostatic interactions play an initial role when KEIF adsorbs to the bilayer surface, followed by a stronger preference for the hydrophobic region of the bilayer, where it finally resides.

To get more insight into the interaction, the systems K-PC¹⁰, K-PC¹⁵⁰, K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰, and K-PC₉PS₁¹⁵⁰ were further investigated with MD simulations. Structural and conformational properties were compared with the K¹⁰, previously published by Koder Hamid et al., 2022 [39]. In Fig. 4, the number density profiles, normalized by the number of atoms in each group, are displayed. In all cases, the profiles are centered around the bilayer to determine its distribution. Generally, the peptide is present within the headgroup region of the bilayer. In K-PC¹⁵⁰, KEIF is the least incorporated into the bilayer. The overlap with the tail region is minimal, while in K-PC¹⁰, PC₉PS₁¹⁰, and K-PC₉PS₁¹⁵⁰, the peptide resides deeper within the bilayer, where K-PC¹⁰ shows the highest relative density furthest into the bilayer. The same behavior is demonstrated in Fig. 5, where the average minimum distance between each amino acid in the peptide sequence and the phosphorus atom in the lipid headgroup is displayed. In K-PC¹⁰, the amino acid closest to the bilayer is an arginine residue at position eight. For the other systems, it is an arginine residue at position 16 that is closest to the bilayer.

The average secondary structure elements of KEIF were compared in the vicinity of the lipid bilayers and in a pure bulk solution; see Table 2. Here it is visible that the peptide becomes more disordered in solution, and the PPII structure decreases in all lipid systems.

3.2. Peptide conformation and structure

3.2.1. In solution

SRCD spectroscopy data were obtained for KEIF in bulk solution, and in the vicinity of negatively charged LUVs, thus K¹⁰, K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰, and K-PC₃PS₁¹⁰. The secondary structure content of KEIF was determined using three analysis methods to corroborate the results: the CDSSTR algorithm on DichroWeb [14], SELCON3, and BeStSel [15,16], which all predict slightly different values. However, qualitatively, the trend is the same. As was previously shown by Jephthah et al. [9] and Koder Hamid et al. [39] using both experimental and computational techniques, KEIF is mainly disordered in aqueous solution with a portion of β -sheets, as shown in Table 3. As shown in Fig. 6, the higher the lipid:KEIF ratio, the more secondary structure present in KEIF. Moreover, a higher portion of negatively charged lipids in the LUVs gives rise to a slightly more structured peptide. Table 3 shows the secondary structure content predicted by the three analysis methods for the highest lipid:peptide ratio, while the data for the remaining ratios is presented in SI (Table S1 and Table S2). Opposed to the results obtained with NR and QCM-D, these data indicate that the electrostatic interactions are cru-

Fig. 3. Quartz-crystal microbalance with dissipation data measured for KEIF upon interaction with a PC_9PS_1 supported lipid bilayer at two different NaCl concentrations, 10 or 150 mM, where K-PC^{10} data is shown in (a) frequency shift, and (b) dissipation shifts of all overtones. K-PC^{150} is shown in (c) frequency shifts and (d) dissipation shifts for all overtones.

Table 2

DSSP analysis of KEIF in solution (K^{10}), or in vicinity of a lipid bilayer ($\text{K-PC}_9\text{PS}_1^{10}$, $\text{K-PC}_9\text{PS}_1^{150}$, K-PC^{10} , PC^{150}) from fully atomistic explicit water molecular dynamics simulations. Values are rounded, and the total percentage, therefore, adds up to more than 100 %.

	K^{10}	$\text{K-PC}_9\text{PS}_1^{10}$	$\text{K-PC}_9\text{PS}_1^{150}$	K-PC^{10}	K-PC^{150}
α -helix	4.0	2.5	0.7	4.9	1.4
β -structure	4.9	10.1	6.5	6.5	9.8
coil/bend/turn	73.2	74.6	78.2	75.1	75.9
PPII	17.9	12.9	14.7	13.5	13.0

cial. It could be because the SRCD spectroscopy is measured directly after mixing, showing only the initial interaction of the peptide with the lipids. As was demonstrated by QCM-D, the interaction with the partially charged bilayer was altered in a time-dependent manner, which implies that what we are measuring with SRCD spectroscopy is the secondary structure elements of the peptide when it is adsorbed to the LUV surface rather than once residing in the hydrophobic region. Furthermore, SRCD spectroscopy measures the average secondary structure elements of all peptide molecules in the sample cell, which means that data is obtained from disordered peptides in solution and more ordered peptides adsorbed to a surface. There are two explanations for this. The first is that a higher lipid:peptide ratio allows more peptides to be adsorbed to the LUV surface, as there are more available LUVs. Secondly, a higher proportion of negatively charged lipids indicates from an electrostatic

perspective that more KEIF molecules will adsorb to the LUV surface. These two arguments combined explain the increasing structural order upon increasing these parameters.

Interestingly, in addition to the decrease in the secondary structure elements labeled as “other”, which includes unordered elements, bends, and turns, a change from β -sheet structure to α -helical structure is observed as a minimum around 220 nm, and it is emerging in the spectra as the lipid:peptide ratio is increased. The increased proportion of structured elements upon adsorption supports the commonly adapted hypothesis that surface-active IDPs gain secondary structure upon adsorption, as the increase in ordered secondary structure elements would protect the hydrophilic amino acids in the sequence from unfavorable interactions with the hydrophobic part of the cell membrane.

Fig. 4. Number density profiles obtained from fully atomistic explicit water molecular dynamics simulations for KEIF, lipid headgroups (hg), lipid tails and water normalized by the number of atoms in each group for (a) K-PC¹⁰, (b) K-PC¹⁵⁰, (c) K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰, and (d) K-PC₃PS₁¹⁵⁰. The orange curve correspond to KEIF, the dark red curve correspond to the lipid headgroups, the dark blue one to the lipid tails, and the teal-dashed line corresponds to the water in the simulation. The density is centered around the bilayer. (For interpretation of the colors in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3

Secondary structure propensity obtained circular dichroism spectroscopy measurements analyzed by CDSSTR, SELCON3, and BeStSel for K¹⁰, K-PC₉PS₁¹⁰ 1:4 peptide:lipid ratio and K-PC₃PS₁¹⁵⁰ 1:4 peptide:lipid ratio. The structure labeled “other” includes unordered elements, bends, and turns.

Method	KEIF			K-PC ₉ PS ₁ ¹⁰ 1:4			K-PC ₃ PS ₁ ¹⁵⁰ 1:4		
	C ^a	S ^b	B ^c	C ^a	S ^b	B ^c	C ^a	S ^b	B ^c
α -helix	2	4	4	15	14	15	22	22	23
β -sheet	32	29	30	25	29	17	20	25	10
other	63	62	66	50	56	69	56	53	67

^a CDSSTR.

^b SELCON3.

^c BeStSel.

3.2.2. In a film

In addition to SRCD spectroscopy measurements in bulk solution, OCD spectroscopy was measured for films of the K¹⁰ and K-PC₃PS₁¹⁰ to obtain information on the orientation of the peptide inserted into the bilayer. Fig. 7 compares the K¹⁰ film and the mixed K-PC₃PS₁¹⁰ film. Measurements with different preparation methods for the K¹⁰ film and films with different lipid:peptide ratios are presented in Figure S3 and Figure S4 to display how this affected the data quality. In producing the K¹⁰ film, the best quality data was obtained when the film was dried rapidly under reduced pressure before rehydration in a humid environ-

ment. For the mixed K-PC₃PS₁¹⁰ films, it was found that a more uniform film was formed as the lipid content increased.

Compared with the SRCD spectroscopy measurements of KEIF in solution, the OCD spectroscopy data indicate that KEIF is more ordered in the film than in the solution and that the peptide organizes more into β -sheet structures rather than α -helical structure. The positive band present between 180 nm to 200 nm is shifted to a higher wavelength for the mixed K-PC₃PS₁¹⁰ film, with a 1:4 peptide to lipid ratio compared to the KEIF film. It is important to note that this could be an effect of absorbance flattening; however, as presented in Figure S4, there are

Fig. 5. Average distance from the bilayer for each amino acid residue, together with its standard deviation for (a) K- PC^{10} , (b) K- PC^{150} , (c) K- $PC_9PS_1^{10}$, and (d) K- $PC_9PS_1^{150}$, obtained from fully atomistic explicit water molecular dynamics simulations. The calculation is performed from the change in minimum distance between each pair over time for the concatenated trajectory of the replicates.

Fig. 6. Synchrotron radiation circular dichroism spectra of K 10 and (a) $PC_9PS_1^{10}$ at peptide:lipid ratios 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4, and (b) $PC_3PS_1^{10}$ at peptide:lipid ratios 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4.

Fig. 7. Oriental circular dichroism spectra of K^{10} and $K\text{-PC}_3\text{PS}_1^{10}$ at a 1:4 peptide:lipid ratio (solid lines, left y-axis) showing a transition from a predominantly β -sheet to α -helical secondary structure. Circular dichroism spectra of K^{10} and $K\text{-PC}_3\text{PS}_1^{10}$ at a 1:4 peptide:lipid ratio (dotted lines, right y-axis) included as a comparison, which shows a less pronounced structural change.

more films composed of KEIF and KEIF+lipids showing similar peak positions with a shift apparent between the two film types, which gives more confidence in the observed difference between the different film compositions. The CD spectroscopy signal for the mixed $K\text{-PC}_3\text{PS}_1^{10}$ film is comparatively more significant than the K^{10} film, with a considerable increase in the signal above 220 nm, suggesting that the structure is more α -helical in the $K\text{-PC}_3\text{PS}_1^{10}$ mixture compared to the K^{10} film. This is, however, not a precise determination as it could be affected by absorbance flattening and scattering. In the paper by Bürck et al. [17], the orientation of an α -helical peptide inserted in a membrane was discussed, where three states were recognized; the peptide parallel to the membrane surface, indicated by a negative band around 208 nm; fully inserted in the membrane, where the CD spectroscopy value around 208 nm is close to zero; a transition from the surface state to the inserted state, where the peptide is partially inserted in a tilted orientation in the membrane, identified by a decrease in negative amplitude around 208 nm, but not yet zero. According to this description, the data obtained for $K\text{-PC}_3\text{PS}_1^{10}$ with a 1:4 peptide:lipid ratio indicates that the peptide is partially inserted into the membrane.

4. Conclusions

We present a detailed characterization of the interactions between KEIF, the N-terminal IDR of the magnesium transporter MgtA, and lipid bilayers mimicking cell membranes. Using a combination of experimental techniques — NR, QCM-D, SRCD, and OCD — alongside MD simulations, we demonstrate that KEIF undergoes a significant conformational change upon adsorption to lipid bilayers. The peptide, which is highly disordered in solution, adopts a more structured conformation, with an increase in α -helical content, and embeds within the hydrophobic tail region of the bilayer. This structural transition is accompanied by the removal of few lipid molecules from the bilayer, and the extent of the interaction depends on the bilayer's charge and on the ionic strength of the surrounding buffer, highlighting the role of electrostatic forces. Fig. 8 provides a schematic illustration of this behavior.

We hypothesize that KEIF's intrinsic disordered nature enables it to respond dynamically to its environment, adopting structured conformations that facilitate its integration into the lipid bilayer and potentially modulate the function of MgtA. This work shows that KEIF can preferentially localize within the hydrophobic tail region of a lipid bilayer, driven by an interplay of hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions, despite their hydrophilic character in solution. The findings challenge traditional paradigms by demonstrating how IDPs balance structural adapt-

ability and surface interactions to perform biological roles. Methodologically, our combination of experimental and computational techniques provides a framework for studying IDP-lipid interactions at atomic resolution.

Future work will focus on increasing and more detailed understanding of the intermolecular interactions regarding the peptide-bilayer interaction by varying the solution's physicochemical properties and extending and expanding the modeling efforts.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Amanda Eriksson Skog: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nykola C. Jones:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Linda K. Månsson:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jens Preben Morth:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Søren Vronning Hoffmann:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Yuri Gerelli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marie Skepö:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marie Skepö reports financial support was provided by Lund University. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2024.12.064>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Fig. 8. A descriptive overview of the three different states that KEIF undergoes upon adsorption to lipid bilayers. From left to right, it is shown that in solution, the peptide is highly disordered, whereas, upon the initial adsorption of large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs), as the middle panel illustrates, the peptide adopts a more structured conformation, with an increase in α -helical content. The right panel visualizes the peptide after incubation in the supported lipid bilayer (SLB) and how the peptide finally embeds within the hydrophobic tail region of the bilayer.

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